

MANAGEMENT OF SCIENTIFIC AND INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS OF PEDAGOGY.

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The today's world is characterized by rapid development of machinery and technologies, as well as a sharp increase in the volume of information and the speed of its transferring and processing. Under these circumstances, the system of professional education faces complex tasks, which require new fundamental approaches to tackle them. Professional activity of modern university teachers carried out in the information and educational environment calls for flexible productive thinking, creativity, highly developed innovative competence to work out and implement effective educational technologies that, in turn, contribute to the formation of innovative competencies in students. The problem of developing readiness for innovation activity is of particular importance for the education of vocational training teachers, which provides the training of teachers for professional education system aimed at training highly qualified personnel for the innovative economy focused on the technologies of tomorrow. In this regard, the issues of improving the innovative pedagogical activity of university teachers [1] and, in particular, its facilitation are becoming even more urgent. The task of forming the readiness of university teachers for innovative pedagogical activity is multifaceted. It is assigned primarily to the teachers themselves, who are expected to constantly improve their professional skills. A modern teacher runs the risk of becoming redundant in the new information society environment unless s/he carries out continuous professional and personal self-development. However, not all teachers have sufficient skills of self-organization, collective problem-solving activity, reflexive techniques, and therefore need facilitation. The task of an educational institution is to provide the required scientific, methodological, informational, psychological and other support to teachers and make favorable conditions for their professional self-implementation. On the one hand, it is necessary to improve the content and methodological aspects of education for the innovative activity of future vocational training teachers in Bachelor's, Master's, and Post-graduate courses offered by vocational training teacher-training universities and faculties, since it is important to lay the foundation for their innovative competence at the stage of training. Moreover, this process can and should be extended to a stage of vocational guidance, when entrants only start choosing their future profession of a vocational training teacher. On the other hand, it is necessary to develop a

system of supplementary vocational education (advanced training, professional retraining), establishing a network of counseling and methodological support for professional activities of teachers.

The development of innovative competence of teachers is of strait-through and implicit nature, encompassing many academic subject courses and various types of educational activities, each of which contributes to the development of readiness for innovations. Nevertheless, a special component – the apical one – can be singled out in the content of vocational teacher training. This component is directly related to the theory and practice of innovative pedagogical activity and represented by a course of “Pedagogical Innovations”. In International The course of “Pedagogical Innovations” reveals the core and regular interrelations of innovative processes in education, studies the processes of creating pedagogical innovations (pedagogical neology), their evaluation and mastery by the pedagogical community (pedagogical axiology), and also practical applications (pedagogical praxeology). “Pedagogical Innovations” helps to answer the three main questions a teachers face in connection with the implementation of innovative pedagogical activity: “What?”, “Why?” and “How?”. The object of research in “Pedagogical Innovations” is precisely the changes in education, but not education itself, and changes in their entirety – from identifying the causes of naturally occurring changes to the artificial design and implementation of pedagogical innovations, and the discovery of the laws of innovation processes [2]. Innovative processes in education are considered in three main aspects: social-and-economic, psychological-andpedagogical and organizational-and-managerial. Basing on this, the content of the “Pedagogical Innovations” course can vary depending on specific features of the professional activity of teachers taking professional development courses. MSc and post-graduate students also have an opportunity to choose certain topics of their interest to research specific innovative processes in education when carrying out projects. The study of pedagogical innovations allows to solve a wide range of problems associated with:

- target and conceptual block of education;
- organizational structure of the education system, educational institutions, education management bodies, the system of advanced training, etc.;
- educational technologies;
- structure and content of education;
- educational programs, textbooks, electronic teaching aids;
- scientific and methodological support of the educational process;

- principles of education management and the quality of education;
- a system for monitoring, diagnosing, controlling and evaluating learning outcomes;

- economic aspects of education, state and interstate policy in education.

When studying pedagogical innovation in the Center for Advanced Training of Teachers, use is made of methods of collective creative activity aimed at organizing knowledge in the context of developing new experience and its personal implications. Of significant didactic value are such types of educational activities as research (stating the problem, putting forward and testing hypotheses, generating ideas, simulating experiments, etc.), discussion (identification and comparison of standpoints, positions, selection and presentation of arguments and so on), modeling (simulation and role-play activities, training sessions), reflexive (intellectual and emotional reflection). These types of educational activities mastered by teachers in the process of professional development are transferrable, i.e. can easily be adapted to the content of subjects they teach. One of the main results of the study of pedagogical innovations by students is not only the psychological readiness for the implementation of innovative activities, but also the technological readiness, which assumes the mastery of innovative educational technologies [3]. The involvement of future teachers in real innovative activities (in the process of conducting master classes, conferences, open laboratories, production practices, performance of course projects and final qualification works basing on real production facilities, etc.) makes the study process possibly isomorphic to the future profession, and thus contributes to further employment of graduates and facilitates their professional adaptation.

B. Innovative Competence of University Teachers

An ability and willingness to carry out innovative activities is considered by many scientists as one of the leading competencies of a modern specialist in the innovation economy [4; 5; 6]. In the framework of competences important for the organization and implementation of innovative activities, there are specific personality characteristics, among which there are professional, personal and specific traits aimed directly at the organization of innovation activity. Professional traits that determine the effectiveness of the organization of innovative activities include functional and creative components, personal traits consist of value orientations and the motivational component, specific traits comprise a high level of professionalism in the field of innovation management, creativity, enterprise, risk taking skills, purposefulness, ability to cooperation, etc. All these traits form the basis for the development of

organizational and communicative competences of innovative activity participants based not so much on the epistemological aspects (development of new information about the organization of innovative activity in the study process), but rather on the psychological aspect (developing a personnel management style, improving the professional image, enhancing empathy and psychological insight, and so on).

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